

**IMPACT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE
OF TEACHING STAFF WORKING IN AUTONOMOUS COLLEGES IN THE TWIN
CITIES OF HYDERABAD AND SECUNDERABAD**

Prof. A. SURYANARAYANA

Former Dean

Faculty of Management

Osmania University

HYDERABAD-500007 (Telangana State),
INDIA.

Dr. B. MOHAN KUMAR

Principal

Badruka College of Commerce & Arts

Telangana State, India HYDERABAD-
500027

ABSTRACT

Education plays a pivotal role in producing qualified human power that accelerates economic development and solves the real problems of a community in particular and the society in general. Students are also expected to spend much of their time on their education and need to graduate with good academic results. However, the trend of graduating students is not proportional to the trend of enrolled students and an increasing number of students seek readmission, suggesting that they did not perform well in their academics. An emotionally intelligent teacher will not only be self-aware but will also demonstrate understanding and empathy towards learners, parents, peers, etc. He also knows well how to manage the teaching-learning process more successfully. Several research studies have shown that emotionally intelligent members of faculty have many and varied skills to more effectively manage the various challenges of daily life. They have a strong influence on students as they encourage growth by spreading a positive atmosphere in the classroom while creating healthy and stimulating environments for learning. They show care for students and create an emotional climate in the classroom that develops the student learning environment and helps the teachers to become more effective to finally ensure academic achievement. Emotional Intelligence (EI) is defined as “The ability to understand one’s emotions, manage them, and understand and effectively manage the emotions of others. ‘Academic Performance’ (AP) is the measurement of student achievement across various academic subjects. Teachers and education officials typically measure achievement using classroom performance, graduation rates, and results from standardized tests. Students’ AP is affected by several factors, which include students’ learning skills, parental background, peer influence, teachers’ quality, and learning infrastructure. An attempt is made in this research-based Paper to examine the impact of EI on AP of teachers working in Autonomous Colleges in the twin cities of Hyderabad and Secunderabad.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence; Academic Performance; Autonomous Professional Colleges; Teaching-Learning Processes

➤ **INTRODUCTION**

“To adapt to the changing world, students must become 21st century students and be equipped with 21st century learning skills. Such students must be taught by a teacher who is a 21st century teacher. The student and the teacher must be in a 21st century school. Students entering the workforce require 21st century skills leading toward employment and entrepreneurship opportunities, job-training programs

and/or military service” (Davis, 2016). However, Emotional Intelligence (EI) helps in building an effective teacher-student relationship. Different kinds of conflicts and misunderstandings between the teacher and the learner can be resolved if teachers are emotionally capable and intelligent. Teaching is intrinsically an emotional practice, given the centrality of emotions in the teaching and learning process. That way, teachers in the 21st

century increasingly have to have skills for responding to classroom emotional situations. Therefore, the way teachers shape and handle their emotional state and those of their learners is central to educational success. Focused on studies carried out that suggest teachers' emotional intelligence like a success indicator for a healthy pedagogical relationship, this chapter makes a reflective approach to the meaning of teachers' emotional intelligence skills in their professional activity (e.g., professional well-being, teacher-student relationship, and student academic achievement). Consequently, it will be necessary to integrate emotional skills in the pre-service teachers' curriculum as skills needed for teaching practice and also to build capacity and support students during challenging times that are constantly changing.

➤ **EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE**

In the words of Goleman (2014), *“Emotional Intelligence (EI) is born largely in the neurotransmitters of the brain’s limbic system, which govern the feelings, impulses, and drives. Research indicates that the limbic system learns best through motivation, extended practice, and feedback”*. EI is defined as “the ability to understand one’s emotions, manage them, and understand and effectively manage the emotions of others (Flutcher 2017, Bradberry & Greaves, 2009; Goleman, 2006; Mayer & Salovey, 1997). Yet another definition by Earnshaw (2015) says EI is the ability to recognize your emotions, understand what they’re telling you, and realize how your emotions affect people around you. It also involves your perception of others: when you understand

how they feel, this allows you to manage relationships more effectively.

➤ **EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF TEACHERS**

‘Teaching and Learning’ are emotional skills that don’t need academic experience also but also interpersonal interactions that create the whole difference and could make the educational process to be highly effective. Most of the research in the education domain pointed out the personal relationships between educators and students where emotions play a significant role so that effective teaching is guaranteed. The effectiveness of the educational process depends largely on the quality of the relationships between the educators and the students. High quality teacher-students relationships can result in effective kind of engagement of the students, which directly leads to effective teaching. It has been proven by numerous researchers that the closeness of relations between educators and students has a very profound effect on the academic achievement of the students. According to Mason, McCune, and Turek (2017), “Interpersonal relationships between teachers and students have been found to affect students’ academic achievement”.

➤ **STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM**

Academic achievement or performance is a *sine qua non* for the successful development of youth of the society in a nation. Learners who perform well in colleges are preparing themselves ably and adequately to make the mandatory transition into adulthood and to achieve professional and economic success. Members of faculty need to be sensitized about the role and relevance of Emotional Intelligence in further honing the skills of

the learners for their professional development to make their careers and future successful and rewarding. In this scenario, it would be highly illuminating to explore and examine the components of EI that act as the contributing factors for academic excellence of the student-learners, especially those pursuing their professional courses in autonomous colleges.

➤ SCOPE OF THE PROBLEM

The present research study is limited only to the members of faculty working in Autonomous Colleges offering Professional Courses such as MBA, MCA, B.E., B. Tech., and B. Pharmacy and located in the twin cities of Hyderabad and Secunderabad of the State of Telangana. Moreover, despite the fact that there are many more variables that may have an impact on the topic of research, the study is confined to an examination of select components of (i) Emotional Intelligence (EI) and (ii) Student Performance. Hence, variables like Self-awareness (**SA**), Self-Management (**SM**), Social Awareness (**SoA**), Social Skills (**SS**), and Relationship Management (**RM**) are studied as the components of EI. Similarly, Student Engagement (**SE**), Instructional Strategies (**IS**), Classroom Management (**CM**), Positive College Climate (**PCC**), Parental Involvement (**PI**), and Community Association (**CA**) are considered as the variables for examining the impact of EI on 'Academic Performance'(AP) of the students.

So, the scope of the study is limited not only to the purposefully selected sample size but also to the deliberately chosen variables.

➤ NEED FOR THE STUDY

The present study is being carried out to identify (i) key components of Emotional

Intelligence (EI) that enhance the emotional capacity and maturity of the Faculty and (ii) the principal impacts the various components of EI are likely to produce on the academic performance and attainments of the student-learners especially those pursuing their professional courses leading to the award of professional degrees such as MBA and BE.

➤ A BRIEF SURVEY OF RELEVANT LITERATURE

It would be in the fitness of things to cite few research studies in this context.

- The study by *Nasser Rahmat (2014)* has concluded that there is a significant and positive relationship between the self-awareness and self-management components of their EI and the educational performance of their students.
- *Nickoo Yamani (2014)* found out that there is an inverse and significant relationship between Scores of EI Components and Job Stress of the Faculty thereby implying that teachers having high EI experience less job stress with an improved capacity to cope with it effectively.
- *Nwadinigwe I.P. (2012)* empirically examined the impact of EI Skills on academic achievement of Senior Secondary School Students and established the relationship between the two among participant groups. A balanced combination and rich admixture of emotional and cognitive minds in training such students has facilitated the identification, recognition, and development of their emotional

competence further contributing to their personal, academic, and career success.

➤ RESEARCH GAP

Earlier studies centering on Emotional Intelligence (EI) mostly focused on working professionals and others servicing the community and society but research involving members of faculty is scanty. A review of research studies related to Higher Learning Institutions (HEIs) strikingly reveals that, *by and large*, they primarily focused on and examined academic performance of the students with research evidence. In depth studies that examined and empirically validated the relationship between EI and Academic Performance are few and far between.

➤ OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To examine the impact of Emotional Intelligence (EI) on the Academic Performance (AP) among the members of Faculty working in Autonomous Colleges offering Professional Courses.
2. To study the relative levels of influence of select components of EI on the individual emotional competencies of such Faculty.
3. To identify and assess the factors contributing to and influencing Academic Performance (AP) of the students of these Autonomous Colleges selected for the study.
4. To make suitable suggestions to members of faculty to enhance their levels of EI leading to an improvement in the AP.

➤ RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

1. **H₀₁:** There is **NO** significant difference between the selected levels of individual components of Emotional Intelligence (EI) and

selected factors that affect Academic Performance (AP).

2. **H₀₂:** There is **NO** correlation between EI and AP.
3. **H₀₃:** There is **NO** correlation between EI and selected factors that affect Academic Performance (AP).
4. **H₀₄:** There is **NO** correlation between select components of EI and AP
5. **H₀₅:** There is **NO** correlation between individual components of EI and selected factors that affect AP.
6. **H₀₆:** There is **NO** good Structural Equation Model Fit of EI on Performance of Faculty.

➤ RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- **Research Design:** Descriptive research design is adopted for the current study. It is going to describe data and characteristics about the population or phenomenon being studied. The relationship or association between variables is demonstrated under the descriptive studies, which answers questions such as “What is” or “What was” and are considered to be the best methods for collecting data that establishes relationships and pronounce the world as it exists.
- **Data Collection:** Primary as well as Secondary data is used for the study. The primary data is collected through structured questionnaires and the secondary data are collected from books, journals, reports, newspapers, websites, etc. A limited literature review is done to understand the concepts of ‘Emotional

Intelligence’ and ‘Academic Performance’.

- **Sample Design:** To examine only a part of the information pertaining to the entire population, non-probability sampling is chosen in such a manner that the total population is divided into groups and the samples are collected from these groups. To choose the sample respondents from these groups, ‘convenience sampling’ technique is used.
- **Sample Size:** Around 350 Members of Faculty (rounded off to the nearest multiple of 50] are chosen for the present study. The size of the sample for the survey is determined by applying the following formula. Sample Size, $n = [ZS/E]^2$
- S=Sample SD from Pilot Study of 50 sample size=0.485
- E=Acceptable Error=5%=0.05; Hence,
Sample size, $n = [1.96*0.485/0.05]^2 = 361.456 = 362$
(Rounded Off to **350**)
- **Development of Questionnaire:** A structured questionnaire is used to collect the data for the study from the members of faculty of Autonomous Professional Colleges in the Twin Cities of Hyderabad and Secunderabad. It covers questions relating to demographic profiles of the respondents, Components of Emotional Intelligence (EI) and factors that have a bearing on Academic Performance (AP). Cronbach’s Alphas is used to test the reliability and these values for the scales used

are above 0.8 signifying thereby very good internal consistency. The content validity of the instrument is verified through the panel of experts from academic and industry and carried out appropriate modifications before launching the main research study.

- **Statistical Tools Used:** Mean, Standard Deviation, Percentage Analysis, Descriptive Statistics, ANOVA, Correlation and Regression Analysis, t-Test, and Structural Equation Model (SEM) are used for the interpretation of the data collected. For the data analysis, SPSS Version 2.0 is used for statistical data analysis.

➤ LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- Autonomous Colleges offering only Professional Courses and situated in the twin cities of Hyderabad and Secunderabad alone are selected for carrying out this study.
- The sample size is pegged down at just 350 respondents.
- Study is limited only to the Members of Faculty whose names appear on the Employment Rolls.

➤ MAJOR FINDINGS

1. Descriptive Statistics

- The results show that around 84.5% of the respondents are titled as “Assistant Professor:
- Three fourths of the participants who took part in the survey are Post Graduates by academic qualification.(78.7%)

- Around half of the respondents (45.3%) come under the age bracket of 25-35 years
- Two thirds (62.5%) of the respondents are Male and the remaining are Female.
- 63.5% of the surveyed faculty members have less than 10 years of experience.

2. *Statistical Findings*

- Members of Faculty carrying different designations do differ in terms of their levels of Self-awareness (SA), Relationship Management (RM), Social Awareness (SoA), Student Engagement (SE), Classroom Management at 1% level of significance and Self Management (SM), Instructional Strategies, Positive College Climate (PCC), Parental Involvement (PI) (at 5% level of significance). Community Involvement (CI) did not significantly vary whenever the designations of the respondents changed.
- Quite understandably, respondents having varying lengths of professional experience tended to possess different levels of SA, SE, IS, CM, and RM (at 1% level of significance) and SA as well as SM (at 5% level of significance).
- Levels of SA, SM, RM, SA, SE, IS, CM, PCC varied significantly between the members of faculty having Post-graduation Qualification and those who don't possess a PG Degree at 5% level of significance.

- Emotional Intelligence (EI) is found to be high for teachers with Under Graduate (UG) qualification alone and **NO** significant difference is noticed in variables such as PI and CI.
- It is inferred through Regression Analysis that SA, SM, and RM significantly influenced AP and contributed to a variance of 65.1%.
- There is a significant correlation between EI and AP. EI has a high positive correlation ($r=0.763$, $p<0.01$) with AP. So, it can safely be concluded that AP increased whenever EI level showed an improvement.
- The SEM fitted for the impact of EI on AP of the members of the faculty is considered "GOOD".

➤ **SUGGESTIONS**

- There is a need for the Female members of faculty to improve their Parental Involvement (**PI**) through an increased level of periodic engagement between them and the parents for longer periods of time to resolve student-related problems thereby also sensitizing the parent about the value and efficacy of such conversations.
- In an effort to improve the levels of Community Involvement (**CI**), more and more intra-college meets need to be organized for the Male members of Faculty and also make them get involved in social activities for the welfare of the community in general.
- Having noticed an EI deficit among the members of faculty who are above 50 years of age, every effort has to be made to conduct

programmes for imparting training in the EI domain specially targeting this older generation of teachers.

- Classes specially targeting the teachers possessing PG Degrees may be designed, developed, and delivered to make them more aware of the importance of EI in their careers.
- Seminars focusing on the overall theme of “Emotional Intelligence” and various other sub-themes that focus on its role, significance, and practical implications need to be organized for the overall benefit of all the members of faculty irrespective of any differences that exist as per the demographic variables.

➤ CONCLUDING COMMENTS

The study has come up with enough empirical evidence to demonstrate a strong and significant association between levels of Self-awareness, Self-management, Social awareness, and Relationship Management possessed by the members of faculty and their Academic Performance. This inference has an immediate practical implication for the administrative and academic leaders of these autonomous professional colleges. Make every effort possible to increase the EI levels of the teachers so that the levels of academic performance of the students would get enhanced. It may be stated unequivocally that EI has the inherent potential and promise to produce and enhance the levels of academic performance.

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